

Stress tolerance—adverse temperature

Cold tolerance of Yunnan rices at early seedling stage

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We screened 2,763 local Yunnan rice varieties for cold tolerance at the early seedling stage during 1987-89. Healthy germinating seeds (100/variety) were chilled at 5 °C for 10 d, then put under sunlight for 10 d. Recovery was assessed on a 1-9 scale, where 1 = highly resistant, 3 = resistant, 5 = medium resistant, 7 = susceptible, 9 = highly susceptible.

We found only 19 highly resistant varieties (less than 3% of those tested). Fifteen originated in Jinping and Shangjiang counties, 2 upland varieties in Changyuan county.

Japonica-lowland-glutinous rice has the best cold tolerance; indica-lowland-

glutinous, the least. Although indica-upland rices had the lowest score and indica-lowland the highest, in general japonicas have significantly greater cold tolerance than indicas, upland rices greater tolerance than lowland, and

nonglutinous greater than glutinous.

The table gives paired comparisons of cold tolerance among 12 forms. The difference in cold tolerance between japonica and indica holds up, but that between lowland and upland and between nonglutinous and glutinous is only partly substantiated. □

Paired comparison of cold tolerance among 12 rice forms in Yunnan, China.

Form	Varieties (no.)	Cold tolerance (av score)	U-value ^a
Indica-upland	17	6.29	1.80
Indica-lowland	1756	8.12	
Japonica-lowland	700	7.25	
Japonica-upland	290	7.46	
Lowland-glutinous	1853	7.94	5.66**
Lowland-nonglutinous	603	7.69	
Upland-nonglutinous	123	7.55	
Upland-glutinous	184	7.28	
Indica-glutinous	1448	8.11	11.45**
Indica-nonglutinous	325	8.07	
Japonica-nonglutinous	401	7.33	
Japonica-glutinous	589	7.30	

^a Significant at 5% (*) and 1% (**) levels.

Comparative performance of indigenous rice varieties for cold tolerance in the hills of Nepal

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Injury due to cold temperature occurs at different stages of rice crop growth in different areas of Nepal, depending on altitude and temperature of irrigation water. Screening of exotic materials from the International Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery at Lumle (1,400 m) has not been promising: most entries showed good cold tolerance at seedling and vegetative stage but failed to produce grain because of incomplete panicle exertion or spikelet sterility. Delayed heading, degeneration of spikelet tips,

and chaffiness of panicles are common symptoms in wetland rice transplanted in Jul above 1,400 m elevation.

Indigenous rice varieties Chhomrong, Seto Bhakunde, and Himali Marshi had performed well at Lumle. We collected 79 indigenous varieties from Lumle and Pakhribas Research Command areas, with altitudes from 700 to 2,000 m asl, and evaluated them at Lumle for cold tolerance and agronomic traits at vegetative and reproductive stages. Mean tempera-

tures at Lumle fall below 20 °C toward the beginning of the reproductive phase (Table 1). Forty-one genotypes showed good cold tolerance at the reproductive stage. Data for the 10 best entries are given in Table 2.

These indigenous germplasm also show good tolerance for diseases associated with low temperature (neck blast *Pyricularia oryzae* and sheath rot *Acrocyndrium oryzae*).

Most materials collected from above

Table 1. Meteorological data for Lumle (28°N 83°E) in 1990.

Month	Av temperature (°C)				Relative humidity (%)	Total rainfall (mm)	Av sunshine (h)
	Max	Min	Mean	Water ^a			
May	23.3	14.6	19.0	NR	82.4	325	5.7
Jun	24.7	17.1	20.9	NR	92.2	1107	4.2
Jul	24.0	17.6	20.8	22.0	97.3	1407	2.1
Aug	23.7	17.4	20.6	20.8	95.2	1088	2.7
Sep	23.5	16.6	20.1	19.6	92.5	978	4.1
Oct	21.1	12.2	16.7	17.8	81.2	315	8.6
Nov	19.3	11.4	15.2	NR	72.3	0	9.3
Mean	22.8	15.3	19.0	20.1	87.6	-	5.2
Total						5220	36.7

^a NR = not recorded.

Table 2. Performance of selected indigenous rice varieties for cold tolerance at LRARC, Nepal, 1990.

Genotype	Altitude ^a (m)	Plant height (cm)	Cold tolerance (1-9) ^b		Spikelet sterility (1-9) ^b	Crop duration (d)	Yield (t/ha) at 12% moisture content
			GS2	GS6			
Silange	1900 NE	111	3	1	2	140	5.3
Chhomrong	2000 NE	137	1	3	1	144	4.1
Kalo Patle Tangle	1600 SE	133	1	1	1	144	4.1
Darmali	1700 NE	160	3	3	1	154	4.1
Dangsing Damadi	1620 SW	130	3	5	1	150	4.0
Phalame	1700 NE	137	1	3	1	143	3.9
Bhuin dhan	1600	125	1	1	1	150	3.8
Bhatte	1700 SE	118	1	1	1	154	3.7
Rato Darmali	1600 W	133	1	1	1	153	3.6
Rato Takmare	1800 SE	117	1	5	1	140	3.6
Range	700-2000	90-151	1-5	1-7	1-5	138-170	0.9-5.3
Mean		125±13.7	2±1.2	2.9±1.7	1.6±1.0	152±29.1	3.05±0.61

^a NE = northeast, SE = southeast, SW = southwest, W = west. ^b By the *Standard evaluation system for rice* GS2 = at tillering, GS6 = at anthesis.

1,500-m altitude that show good cold tolerance had dark grains. They will be grouped according to phenology and plant height for further use in cold tolerance breeding.

Thorough collection and evaluation of local rice germplasm would help identify donors of cold tolerance at anthesis, currently lacking in our breeding program. □

Screening for cold tolerance in Nepal

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Rice is grown in all agroecological zones of Nepal, from the foothills to the high mountains. Double cropping is practiced up to about 900 m, and rice reaches its altitudinal limit at 2,000 m.

Chilling injury limits both the rice-producing area and the length of the growing season. Above 1,000-m altitude, cool weather and cold irrigation water cause delayed heading, leaf yellowing, partial panicle exertion, spikelet degeneration, spikelet sterility, and low yields in wetland rice transplanted in July. Poor germination and slow seedling growth are additional symptoms in irrigated short-duration rice seeded in Feb below 900 m.

Of 31 rice varieties recommended so far by the National Rice Research Program, only Khumal 2 and Palung 2

sited below 500 m asl, in the lower hills and the Terai.

Cold stress in rice occurs at specific growth stages in different altitude regime (Fig. 1), and cold tolerance nurseries have been established at off-station research (OSR) sites to include both the diversity and complexity of high-altitude rice production systems.

At Tapu (1,000 m), mean air temperature does not fall below 20°C until the crop reaches spikelet filling. At Lumle (1,400 m), mean air temperature does not fall below 20°C until the beginning of the reproductive stage. At Chhomro (2,000 m), mean air temperature is low (15-20°C) throughout the growing season. Water temperatures recorded at Lumle and Chhomro during anthesis are 19.1-21.2 and 15.0-21.2 °C, respectively.

At Tapu, chilling injury in rice is induced by cool air temperatures around ripening time; at Lumle and Chhomro, it is attributed to both cold weather and cold water, and to their durations, at different growth stages.

We evaluated four sets of National Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery, including both indigenous and exotic rice genotypes, at Yampaphant (475 m), Tapu, Lumle, and Chhomro during 1987 and 1988. (Since 1985, 79 local and 528 exotic entries have

been released for cold tolerance in the midhills. Their performance above 1,400 m asl is poor.

This is not surprising: breeding for low temperature tolerance in Nepal is limited because most research stations are

1. Temperature and rainfall patterns at Lumle (1400 m), Chhomro (2000 m), and Tapu (1000 m) testing sites in Nepal. Data are averages of 10 yr (1980-89), 4 yr (1986-89), and 3 yr (1987-89), respectively. Legend: (○—○) = max temp °C; (△—△) = mean temp °C; (●—●) = min temp °C.